

Decoding Segregation: The relational landscape of segregation research and a bottom-up ontology of forms

Supplementary information summary

This Zenodo repository contains the Supplementary Information (SI) associated with the article “Decoding Segregation: The topological landscape of segregation research and a bottom-up ontology of forms.” The present summary provides an overview of the SI structure and describes the contents of each section. It includes additional analyses, coding protocols, datasets, interactive visualisations, high-resolution figures, and computational resources that could not be accommodated in the main manuscript. All materials are available below as individual, downloadable files corresponding to the respective SI components.

1. Additional analyses

1.1. Intersectionality in segregation research.

1.2. Knowledge production networks:

- Co-citation network of works in segregation research
- Co-authorship network across countries
- Co-citing journals

2. Codebook for identifying segregation forms

Protocol for interpretive procedure ('coding') of identifying n-grams as representations ('labels') of segregation forms (SFs).

3. Supplementary tables (CSV files)

3.1 *STable_1_n_papers_discipline.*

Number of papers per discipline including the 169 fields indexed in Scopus' ASJC.

3.2 *STable_2_first_countries_year_publication*

Segregation-related publications including information of year, country and number of papers. Data file for figure 1b.

3.3 *STable_3_combinatorial_accretion*

SFs combinatorial accretion, including first year of SF1 and SF2, and first year of co-occurrence and trigram

3.4 *STable_4_network_properties_evolution*

3.5 *STable_5_louvain_clusters*

3.6 *STable_6_first_year_vs_centrality*

SFs first year of publication, degree of centrality and betweenness centrality.

3.7 *STable_7_first_cooc_information_nodes*

3.8 *STable_8_top_15_ngrams_per_discipline*

3.9 *STable_9_n_papers_year_continent_prop*

Number of papers per continent each year, and the proportion relative to the total number of papers published in the year.

3.10 *STable_10_n_papers_year_country_prop*

Number of papers per country each year and the proportion relative to the total number of papers published in the year.

3.11 *STable_11_ontology_labelling*

3.12 *STable_12_node_information_cocitation_documents.*

3.13 *STable_13_node_information_authorship_countries.*

3.14 *STable_14_node_information_coupling_sources*

3.15 *STable_15_segregation_n-grams*

4. Interactive graphs

The HTML files below can be downloaded and opened in any browser:

4.1 *_Fig_01d_Proportion of SFs per year*

Proportion of segregation forms published per year

4.2 *_Fig_01e_Distribution of disciplinary fields in segregation forms*

Distribution of disciplinary fields in segregation forms, showing a total of 169 fields indexed in Scopus.

4.3 *_Fig_11a_Share of SR publications by world region.*

Segregation research publications as a share of all publications in subject areas by world region.

4.4 *_Fig_11b_Share of SR publications by country.*

Segregation research publications as a share of all publications in subject areas by country.

4.5 *_Fig_11c_Map_share of SR publications by country.*

Segregation research publications as a share of all publications mapped by country.

4.5 *Fig. 12c:* <https://segregation-ontology.cityscience.group/>

5. Semantic grouping of segregation terms

Code used to create semantic grouping of segregation terms. Includes the input data as CSV, an output PDF and the output hierarchical branch table used for the manual subsequent grouping.

6. Scopus search string

Code used to identify n-grams in files obtained from the Scopus database.

7. Code availability

7.1 processing dataset.R

Processes the raw data by cleaning text (lowercasing, removing punctuation) and extracting/refining n-grams (forms of segregation) from titles, abstracts and keywords, resulting in a core dataset with identified n-grams.

7.2 defining countries.R

Defines and extracts the countries and continents/regions of the authors' affiliations in the dataset, including standardizing country names and identifying the first author's country.

7.3 defining disciplines.R

Defines the disciplines for the publications by replacing ASJC codes with their respective discipline names, calculating the number of disciplines per paper, and isolating the first listed discipline.

7.4 tables.R

Cleans final data columns and generates various summary tables, counts, and cross-tabulations.

7.5 charts.R

Generates and saves several charts (data visualizations) from the aggregate tables.

7.6 co-occurrence network.R

Prepares the n-gram data and calculates the co-occurrence network edges by determining how often different n-grams appear together within publications for each year, creating the base data for the network graphs.

7.7.1 creating networks pt 1.R

Creates the co-occurrence network graph, calculates network metrics, and exports the network and its time-sliced versions in Pajek format (.net).

7.7.2 creating networks pt 2.R

Edits time-evolution network .json files (after external processing) to standardize node attributes, specifically replacing the cluster and coordinate (x, y) information for consistency.

7.7.3 creating networks pt 3.R

Determines the community structure of the full co-occurrence network using the Louvain algorithm, assigns clusters to each n-gram, and updates the main network's.json visualization file.

7.8 Original and preponderant disciplines.R

Analyses the disciplinary field by calculating the original discipline (first appearance) and the preponderant discipline (highest count) for each segregation form (n-gram) to track disciplinary changes over time.